

Smart Sector Grouping for Increased Flexibility of Air Traffic Controller Validations

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Abstract— The increasing complexity of European air traffic, together with persistent capacity shortages in Air Traffic Service Units (hereinafter ATSU) created the need for innovative approaches to optimise Air Traffic Controller (hereinafter ATCO) allocation and sector management. In this context, the SESAR project IFAV3 (Increased Flexibility of ATCO Validation) was initiated, encompassing four complementary strategies. This paper focuses on the validation of the Smart Sector Grouping (SSG) strategy, which is divided into two complementing use cases. The first addresses ATCO rostering process aiming to improve the flexibility and efficiency of controller allocation. The second introduces the SSG process-tool, designed to support Airspace Managers (hereinafter ASMs) in defining optimal sector groups within an ATSU improving the current method, thereby maximising the potential of the IFAV concept. Two validation exercises were conducted, one in Sweden and one in Spain, to assess the feasibility, operational benefits, and impact of the strategy. Results of both use cases suggest that Smart Sector Grouping can reduce workload, improve decision-making, and enhance the efficient use of ATCO qualifications without compromising safety.

Keywords— Air Traffic Management, Air Traffic Controller (ATCO), Flexible Rostering, Smart Sector Grouping (SSG), Sector Configuration, IFAV Project, SESAR.

I. INTRODUCTION

To manage air traffic efficiently, airspace is organized into smaller sections called sectors. To operate in a specific sector, an ATCO must hold a license with a rating and a unit endorsement, obtained by general and sector specific training. Once certified, ATCOs are required to complete refresher training at regular intervals and perform a minimum number of working hours per sector. Consequently, each controller is typically qualified to operate only in a limited number of sectors, to safeguard efficiency and safety. Given the complexity of the qualification procedure and the shortages and growing demand for ATCOs capable of working across multiple sectors, Air

Navigation Service Providers (ANSPs) face a staffing-rostering challenge.

Within every Air Traffic Services Unit (hereinafter ATSU), there are several unit endorsements that establish which sectors an ATCO is allowed to control. Grouping sectors into unit endorsements is critical, as it influences the number of controllers who are both needed and available to meet the traffic demand at each sector at each given moment. Currently, sector grouping is carried out by ASMs, who also need to decide on how many ATCOs are to be trained for each endorsement. This is done without any standardised technological support tools or complicated methods, even though this process involves a optimisation problem: factors such as an estimation of traffic demand, training costs, sector specifics, shift constraints, qualification requirements, and complexity, for example, due to weather and non-nominal activity need to be considered.

The Increased Flexibility of ATCO Validation (hereinafter IFAV) solution for En-Route control addresses the challenge of maximising flexible rostering of the ATCOs. Multiple strategies were developed to reduce ATCOs' mental effort, optimise resource allocation, and standardise practices across units. These strategies include tool support to help ATCOs manage unfamiliar airspace, competency and experience assessments to enable flexible rostering, and smart sector grouping to balance traffic demand with controller availability.

In addition, the Common Unit Competence Scheme framework proposes a global methodological approach across Europe to accommodate current and future currency requirements accepted by ANSPs and local National Competent Authorities, while respecting current regulation (EU 2015/340 [1]). Based on this common methodology, different innovative strategies are being validated within the project to allow a larger number of sectors an ATCO is endorsed for without impacting negatively on safety.

A. Smart Sector Grouping Strategy

One of the innovative strategies proposed within the IFAV3 project is Smart Sector Grouping. SSG aims to support airspace management with tools to define the best ATSU organisation for optimisation of human resources and automation of the licensing process. SSG is a data-driven approach that takes into account the complex interplay between sectors geography, traffic flow, and resources. The goal of SSG is to identify the most efficient combinations of sectors for unit endorsements, enabling the optimal use of available ATSU resources and forecasting future manpower requirements.

B. Related work

The IFAV3 solution was developed within the SESAR program and builds on previous research from PJ.10-06 NGCV, PJ.10-W2-73 IFAV, and PJ.33-W3-01a FALCO [2]. A joint exercise (NATS, Skyguide, LFV) under Solution PJ.10-06 in 2018 showed that controllers faced challenges when working in unfamiliar sectors due to different procedures, coordination, and geography, influencing situation awareness and workload. This highlights the importance of support tools and adaptations and indicated that maintaining safety and performance may require adjustments to controller workload and airspace capacity, offering valuable guidance for future development.

The projects PJ.10-W2-73 IFAV and PJ.33-W3-01a aimed to reduce controllers' reliance on detailed memorised sector knowledge by moving toward standardised procedures, additional dedicated supporting tools, and adapted briefing and training. PJ.10-W2-73 explored procedural measures to help controllers work safely in unfamiliar environments, improving rostering flexibility but potentially reducing individual productivity until full measures are in place. It also raised considerations for training, licensing, and standardisation. PJ.33-W3-01a validation exercises showed that using dedicated supporting tools and procedures in unfamiliar environments had a positive impact on safety, workload, and situation awareness. The approach also demonstrated potential to shorten training, reduce endorsement maintenance, and improve cost efficiency at the network level.

Staff planning and rostering of ATCOs has long been recognised as a critical factor in ensuring capacity and cost efficiency in an ATSU. Inefficient rostering has contributed to significant delays in Europe, with over 60% of air traffic flow management (hereinafter ATFM) delays in 2019 attributed to staffing and capacity issues [3, 4]. Earlier European programs such as EATCHIP and EATMP established methodologies for manpower planning [5, 6], while subsequent studies examined Human Factors issues involving fatigue [7, 8] and automation [9]. Together with evidence showing that delay costs often exceed the costs of additional staffing [10], these studies highlight potential efficiency gains through optimised ATCO rostering.

From an optimisation perspective, ATCO rostering is a complex scheduling problem, with research contributions ranging from formal problem definitions and optimisation frameworks for remote tower centres [11] and metaheuristic

methods such as variable neighbourhood search [12, 13]. Recent work has shifted towards systematically linking rostering practices with operational outcomes. Pavlović et al. [14] proposed a mathematical model relating daily capacity profiles, rostering flexibility, and staffing needs, demonstrating its application on three European ATSUs. Moreover, a two-phase mathematical modelling approach was developed to identify potential network-level efficiency gains from cross-border delegation of air traffic services, following recent adoption of the SES2+ regulation [15]. The results show that strategic pairing of ACC could achieve up to 74% of theoretical staffing savings and provide guidance for policymakers and network managers. The findings emphasise the impact of rostering on spare capacity and ANSP performance.

C. The current paper

In this paper, we explore the benefits of the proposed SSG, presenting the tools for implementation of the proposed solution that maximises the capacity of the ATSU. We present the methodology and the results of two European airspace use case validations, which demonstrate applications of the same overall strategy but with complementary approaches. The Swedish use case (Section II) focuses on mathematical optimisation and modelling to determine theoretical bounds and showcase the benefits of SSG through optimised rostering. The Spanish use case (Section III) employs a data-intensive analysis, combining extensive traffic data with brute-force combinatorial techniques, to support the design of Endorsement-based Sector Grouping, leveraging a user-oriented tool. Both approaches aim at assisting decision-makers in implementing the SSG strategy in practice. Finally, Section IV concludes the paper by merging the findings from both use cases.

II. USE-CASE SWEDEN

The Swedish approach aims to validate the Smart Sector Grouping (SSG) concept by running calculations that optimize ATCO shift scheduling and improve resource use within a more flexible rostering environment.

A. Swedish Airspace Structure

In Sweden FIR there are two Areas of Responsibility AOR, with one Air Traffic Control Centres (ATCC) each, located in Malmö and in Stockholm. Both of the centres are handling mainly en-route traffic, meaning that ATCOs mainly have the Area Control Surveillance (ACS) rating.

Stockholm's Area of Responsibility (AoR) is from just south of Stockholm to the northernmost point in Sweden. Stockholm ATCC is responsible for 11 en-route sectors (Figure 1, sectors with red contours). The ATCOs are divided into two various endorsement groups named Y and Z. These groups are fixed with no overlapping endorsement.

Malmö's AoR is from the southern part of the Baltic sea to the border of Stockholm AoR. Malmö ATCC is responsible for 10 sectors (Figure 1, sectors with pink contours). The ATCOs are divided into two various endorsement groups, Yellow and Red. The difference compared to Stockholm, is that Malmö has a third endorsement group consisting of a few fixed sectors

from the Yellow and Red group. This third overlapping endorsement group can work flexible in the Red or the Yellow group depending on the need.

Figure 1. Swedish en-route sectors, controlled from ATCC Stockholm (red) and ATCC Malmö (pink)

The traffic load in the sectors is measured in traffic counts, the number of flights present in a defined sector at a specific time, also mentioned as occupancy. The value of the occupancy, where the managers are splitting or combining sectors, may vary from one sector to another, but is a set value for each sector or sector combination (e.g. orange line in Figure 2 corresponds to the peak occupancy in the example sector). The value is set based on the long-term experience from the controllers who hold the corresponding endorsement in the sector or sector combination. Although, there are other factors rather than the occupancy that are influencing the decision-making process (such as weather, non-nominal events and other complexity factors).

Figure 2. Traffic load in the example sector at ATCC Arlanda Stockholm on October 11, 2022

B. Methodology

The combinations of sectors within the endorsements are limiting the ways how the ATCOs can be assigned to the open sectors during the shift. We propose an optimisation modelling solution for optimal ATCO shift scheduling, which inputs the feasible sector combinations together with all the operational shift constraints and outputs the minimum number of controllers and their optimal assignments. The idea is to use this approach to investigate whether the introduction of new sector combinations within the ATCO endorsements can result in better human resource utilization.

1) Optimisation model

In this subsection, we present the mathematical formulation of the ATCO rostering optimization. The model is a modification of the dispatcher shift scheduling problem [16]. The aim is to create a schedule (roster) which assigns a qualified controller to a sector combination, respecting constraints on the duration of controllers' shifts and breaks, and the necessity to hold the corresponding endorsements. The problem is formulated as a Mixed-Integer Linear Program (MILP), which in general is NP-hard (Nondeterministic Polynomial time; meaning no efficient algorithm is known to solve the problem in all cases). However, smaller instances of the problem can be solved using commercial off-the-shelf optimisation software, as we demonstrate in the experimental part of this study (Subsection II-B2). The constraints on the shift length and resting periods are modelled based on the strong formulation for min/max on/off sequences [17], including a crew usage variable [18].

Input: A set of ATCC en-route sectors is given with their traffic load per time period, including aircraft movements, climbing and descending aircraft. Feasible sector combinations are also provided, considering sector borders, traffic flow and volume. We assume that there are enough ATCOs holding the corresponding endorsements to be assigned to each feasible sector combination.

Output: The optimal number of ATCOs to cover all the traffic in all the sectors and their optimal assignment to the sector combinations with respect to the constraints.

Constraints: The following constraints are integrated reflecting the safety and efficiency requirements for ATCC personnel operation:

- Maximum number of movements per controller
- Only one controller is to be assigned to each sector
- Only ATCOs holding the corresponding endorsement can be assigned to the sector
- Upper and lower bound on controller shift length
- Maximum continuous time "in position" without break
- Maximum number of switches between the assigned sector combinations for two consecutive time periods.

The objective function of the given model is the total number of assigned controllers. The complete mathematical model is provided in Figure 3.

TABLE I. OPTIMIZATION MODEL PARAMETERS

Parameters	Description
C	set of air traffic controllers, indexed by i
S	set of en-route control sectors, indexed by j
P	set of time periods, indexed by k
A	set of sector combinations, indexed by l
$TL_{j,k}$	task load in sector j during period k
TL^{\max}	maximum allowed task load per controller
$e_{i,j} \in 0,1$	=1 if controller i holds an endorsement for sector j
$a_{l,j} \in 0,1$	=1 if sector j is an element of sector combination l
T^{\min}	minimum shift length (in time periods)
T^{\max}	maximum shift length (in time periods)
R^{\min}	minimum number of rest periods between two shifts
$p = P $	number of time periods in the time horizon
W^{\max}	Maximum number of periods of consecutive work before a scheduled break
X^{\max}	Maximum number of allowed switches in sector combinations assigned to a controller during the two consecutive time periods

TABLE II. OPTIMIZATION MODEL VARIABLES

Variables	Description
$c_{i,l,k} \in 0,1$	=1 if controller i is assigned sector combination l during period k
$y_{i,k} \in 0,1$	=1 if controller i is at work during period k
$v_{i,k} \in 0,1$	=1 if controller i starts a shift at the beginning of period k
$q_i \in 0,1$	=1 if controller i is on duty during some period
$w_{i,k}$	number consecutive periods including period k when controller i is at work
$x_{i,l,k} \in 0,1$	= 0 if controller i is assigned the same sector combination l during periods k and $k+1$

Constraints (1) and (2) guarantee the minimum and maximum shift length, by assuring that whenever a controller starts a shift at some period, this shift can end only after at least T^{\min} working periods and end no later than after T^{\max} working periods. Constraints (3) and (4) connect the variables $y_{i,k}$ and $v_{i,k}$. Constraints (5) and (6) connect the variables $v_{i,k}$ and q_i , by assuring that once a controller i starts a shift at any period then the correspondent q_i is set to 1. Constraint (7) assures the minimum rest periods between two consecutive shifts by prohibiting any controller from starting a new shift within R^{\min} periods after finishing a previous one. Constraint (8) prohibits the assignment of sector combinations to a controller where the total taskload exceeds TL^{\max} . The binary parameter a_{ij} is equal to 1 whenever sector j is an element of sector combination l . Constraint (9) allows a sector combination to be assigned only to a controller endorsed for all sectors in the combination. Constraint (10) ensures that whenever a controller is at work,

they should be assigned exactly one sector combination, except for the combination labelled with 0, which in this formulation stands for the empty assignment that is assigned to the controllers at their break according to Constraint (11). Constraint (12) ensures that each sector combination should be assigned to exactly one controller for any time period. Constraint (13) ensures that during the shift the worker is either at work or at break and the sum of work and break periods constitute the total shift length. Constraint (14) ensures that controllers can only be assigned one sector combination at each time they are “in position”. Constraint (15) calculates and assigns the values for number of consecutive periods including k controller i is at work to variable $w_{i,k}$. Constraint (16) ensures that a controller does not work more than W^{\max} periods before their break. Constraints (17-19) implement the restriction on the number of switches between the assigned sector combinations for each controller for the consecutive time periods.

2) Experimental set-up

To showcase the application of the proposed optimization framework, example rosters were constructed for the day-time operation (from 06:00-22:00) during two consecutive days (October 11-12 2022) for ATCC Stockholm and Malmö. Real traffic movement data provided by LFV was used, which defined the task load in each sector per time period (occupancy numbers). The maximum number of movements in sectors is defined by the limitations in the occupancy of the sectors and is unified for ATCC Stockholm to 25, and 44 for ATCC Malmö.

The assignment period is 30 minutes, with shift lengths ranging from 1 to 8 hours (16 time periods) and a minimum 16 time periods between shifts. Maximum number of allowed switches in sector combinations varied between the scenarios.

The sector combination sets in our three scenarios for optimized sector grouping were defined as follows:

- **Current:** contains the actual sector combinations used during the example days in operation.
- **Feasible:** contains all the current sector combinations as well as new complementing combinations justified by operational experts (ATCOs and supervisors).
- **Neighbours:** contains all possible combinations with maximum five geographical neighbouring sectors.

The model was implemented using *AMPL* modeling language and Gurobi optimizer version 9.5.1 as a solver, utilising a powerful server featuring Intel HNS2600BPB computer nodes with 32 CPU cores, 384 GB, provided by the National Academic Infrastructure for Supercomputing in Sweden (NAISS) [20]. Computational time ranges from 20 minutes to 12 hours and depends strongly on the value of the parameter X^{\max} in the constraint (19), which restricts the number of allowed switches between the assignments for consecutive time periods—lower values of this parameter make it more difficult for the optimizer to solve the problem.

$$\sum_{\mu=k+1-T}^{\kappa} v_{i,\mu(\text{mod } p)} \leq y_{i,k} \quad \forall i \in C, \forall k \in P \quad (1)$$

$$\sum_{\mu=k+1-T}^k v_{i,\mu(\text{mod } p)} \geq y_{i,k} \quad \forall i \in C, \forall k \in P \quad (2)$$

$$v_{i,k} \geq y_{i,k} - y_{i,k-1(\text{mod } p)} \quad \forall i \in C, \forall k \in P \quad (3)$$

$$v_{i,k} \leq y_{i,k} \quad \forall i \in C, \forall k \in P \quad (4)$$

$$v_{i,k} \leq q_i \quad \forall i \in C, \forall k \in P \quad (5)$$

$$\sum_{k \in P} v_{i,k} \geq q_i \quad \forall i \in C \quad (6)$$

$$\sum_{\mu=k+1}^{k+R} v_{i,\mu(\text{mod } p)} \leq q_i - y_{i,k} \quad \forall i \in C, \forall k \in P \quad (7)$$

$$\sum_{j \in S} c_{i,l,k} \cdot a_{l,j} \cdot TL_{j,k} \leq TL^{\max} \quad \forall i \in C, \forall k \in P, \forall l \in A \quad (8)$$

$$c_{i,l,k} \leq e_{i,j} \quad \forall i \in C, \forall l \in A, \forall j \in S, \forall k \in P \quad (9)$$

$$\sum_{l \in A \setminus \{0,1\}} c_{i,l,k} = y_{i,k} \quad \forall i \in C, \forall k \in P \quad (10)$$

$$c_{i,0,k} = 1 - y_{i,k} \quad \forall i \in C, \forall k \in P \quad (11)$$

$$\sum_{l \in A \setminus \{0,1\}} \sum_{i \in C} a_{l,j} \cdot c_{i,l,k} = 1 \quad \forall k \in P, \forall j \in S \quad (12)$$

$$c_{i,1,k} + c_{i,l,k} \leq 1 \quad \forall i \in C, \forall k \in P, \forall l \in A \setminus \{1\} \quad (13)$$

$$\sum_{l \in A \setminus \{0,1\}} c_{i,l,k} \geq y_{i,k} - c_{i,1,k} \quad \forall i \in C, \forall k \in P \quad (14)$$

$$\sum_{kk=k}^{k+W^{\max}-1} y_{i,kk(\text{mod } p)} - c_{i,1,kk(\text{mod } p)} = w_{i,k} \quad \forall i \in C, \forall k \in P \quad (15)$$

$$c_{i,1,k+W^{\max}(\text{mod } p)} \geq \frac{1}{W^{\max}} \cdot w_{i,k} - \frac{W^{\max} - 1}{W^{\max}} \quad \forall i \in C, \forall k \in P \quad (16)$$

$$x_{i,l,k} \geq c_{i,k} - c_{i,k+1(\text{mod } p)} \quad \forall i \in C, \forall l \in A, \forall k \in P \quad (17)$$

$$x_{i,l,k} \geq c_{i,k+1(\text{mod } p)} - c_{i,k} \quad \forall i \in C, \forall l \in A, \forall k \in P \quad (18)$$

$$\sum_{i \in C} \sum_{l \in A} \sum_{k \in P} x_{i,l,k} \leq X^{\max} \quad (19)$$

Objective function:

$$\min \sum_{i \in C} q_i \quad (20)$$

Figure 3. Optimization model for ATCO rostering problem in application to the Smart Sector Grouping strategy for Increased Flexibility of ATCO Validations.

period/ sector	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31
	6:00	6:30	7:00	7:30	8:00	8:30	9:00	9:30	10:00	10:30	11:00	11:30	12:00	12:30	13:00	13:30	14:00	14:30	15:00	15:30	16:00	16:30	17:00	17:30	18:00	18:30	19:00	19:30	20:00	20:30	21:00	21:30
1-Y	6	7	15	5	7	6	5	6	5	14	12	16	8	4	17	16	20	11	8	12	7	4	6	8	16	11	9	8	13	8	6	3
2	7	10	7	10	17	7	5	4	12	8	7	7	9	5	9	18	6	2	14	12	11	5	10	6	9	7	4	11	8	5	6	3
3	5	10	5	7	6	15	9	7	8	7	6	4	8	6	8	9	10	3	6	7	10	6	5	7	7	10	10	9	6	8	4	3
4	10	10	4	10	10	6	8	10	14	12	12	7	13	8	11	12	7	8	7	9	12	9	10	5	8	7	7	9	7	8	8	1
5	10	7	4	11	8	3	7	9	11	8	10	7	10	7	11	7	8	5	6	6	10	5	7	6	6	5	4	6	8	4	2	3
6	6	5	4	5	4	5	7	5	10	10	10	10	14	9	8	9	6	7	7	6	1	5	7	8	11	11	5	8	5	4	4	2
7	4	7	4	8	7	4	5	7	6	13	8	8	3	5	11	12	14	8	11	9	2	8	6	6	14	10	5	6	3	3	6	0
8	6	8	3	9	11	7	9	5	3	12	13	10	10	8	11	18	8	8	9	7	9	6	3	7	10	10	5	6	2	6	5	4
9	8	7	4	5	5	4	6	8	10	10	8	7	5	8	7	7	4	9	5	6	7	2	6	7	8	8	8	5	4	6	2	1
10-W	7	14	10	10	19	14	6	9	12	10	5	17	8	10	16	17	16	9	10	10	17	7	8	14	8	15	6	18	13	7	5	6

Figure 4. Example optimized roster for one day assignment of 15 ATCOs to 10 en-route sectors at ATCC Malmö on October 11, 2022 (Current scenario).

The resulting rosters can be visualised as illustrated in Figure 4, where the columns correspond to time periods (half an hour in this example), rows contain sectors, and the cells contain the number of movements in the corresponding sector during the chosen period (with high traffic numbers highlighted). Colours of the cells represent controller assignments (each controller is assigned to sector combinations containing several sectors).

To compare the resulting assignments for different scenarios, the following performance indicators (PIs) are used:

- **Controllers:** minimum number needed (one per position)
- **Switches:** changes in the assignment to sector combinations for the consecutive time periods
- **Average:** number of assigned ATCOs per period
- **Threshold:** maximum task load in sector combination one ATCO can manage during the given time period
- **Peak:** number of occurrences when task load assigned to one ATCO per time period is close to the threshold
- **COE (Coefficient of Efficiency):** ratio between the number of time periods controllers are in position to the total number of periods they spent at work.

3) Validation exercise

In the validation workshops, one for each unit (Stockholm & Malmö), operational experts (n=11) were introduced to the SSG concept and the results of three proposed scenarios. The workshops covered various discussion topics, including the usability, scenario preferences, rostering and operational feasibility, and the potential safety and human performance impact. Participants shared their perspectives on the topics through discussions and questionnaires.

C. Results

Scenario	Controllers minimum (executive)	Switches during shift	Average controllers per period	Threshold maximum taskload	Peak >=20 taskload occurrences	COE* % worktime @ position	Combi Used combinations
Real		16 x	3.9	31	8	0.62	1
Current opt	9	80	3	25	15	0.67	1
Feasible	8	100	2.84	25	30	0.71	4
Neighbors	8	130	3	25	27	0.76	21
22% efficiency improvement							

Figure 5 and Figure 6 illustrate the example results for day 1 (October 11, 2022) for Stockholm and Malmö ATCC, respectively. A 12-26% improvement was observed in the coefficient of performance for the third scenario (neighbour) in

comparison to the currently implemented one. For ATCC Stockholm Arlanda, noticeable improvement is achieved when more sector combinations (47 instead of 10) are introduced already in the feasible scenario, while in ATCC Malmö the best result is obtained for the third scenario combining neighbouring sectors (with 198 input combinations).

Scenario	Controllers minimum (executive)	Switches during shift	Average controllers per period	Threshold maximum taskload	Peak >=20 taskload occurrences	COE* % worktime @ position	Combi Used combinations
Real		16 x	3.9	31	8	0.62	10
Current opt	9	80	3	25	15	0.67	10
Feasible	8	100	2.84	25	30	0.71	47
Neighbors	8	130	3	25	27	0.76	216
22% efficiency improvement							

Figure 5. Validation results for Stockholm ATCC, October 11, 2022

Scenario	Controllers minimum (executive)	Switches during shift	Average controllers per period	Threshold maximum taskload	Peak >=20 taskload occurrences	COE* % worktime @ position	Combi Used combinations
Real		17 x	6.4	72	11	0.66	9
Current opt	15	184	4	44	4	0.65	9
Feasible	10	110	3.9	44	5	0.72	22
Neighbors	7	110	2.97	44	11	0.75	198
13% efficiency improvement							

Figure 6. Validation results for Malmö ATCC, October 11, 2022

Finally, from the resulting assignments, we can derive the combinations of the sectors for which the corresponding ATCOs have to be trained for, as well as the most useful sector combinations (the ones used in the resulting optimised assignments). This information is critical for understanding which sector combinations should be used for improving future controller endorsements, which will provide more flexibility for constructing optimised rosters.

The main findings from the validation exercise were that participants believe SSG can improve efficiency and support future unit endorsement grouping. They also stress the importance of considering traffic flow and scale besides bordering and reducing the number of switches when making the sectors and sectorisation pathways over the course of a shift, as it would make the solution more operationally attainable. Hence, the “feasible” scenario, which includes traffic flow to determine sector combinations (41% of participants) was the preferred scenario. Participants rated the solution relatively low on feasibility (6.4/10), although both the solution and the IFAV concept were viewed more favourably at the end of the validation workshop compared to the beginning. The anticipated impact on safety and human performance was considered minor, with only limited indirect effects expected.

Finally, in the Malmö case, there are already some overlapping controller endorsements, which may inspire the next step within the SSG solution, which concerns the possibility of integrating rosters of the Stockholm and Malmö units with IFAV controllers in the bordering sectors during low complexity situations.

III. USE-CASE SPAIN

The aim of the Spanish approach is to develop a Smart Sector Grouping tool (hereinafter *GRU*) to support ASMs in strategically designing, years in advance, the optimal sector grouping structure, complementing the optimised ATCO shift scheduling (the Sweden use-case).

This tool enables the identification of the most suitable sector groupings to support unit endorsements, accommodate future traffic demand, and maximize the effective use of available ATS resources, all within a new and more flexible ATCO rostering environment.

In conclusion, the GRU tool is proposed as a decision-support tool for ASMs to design the most optimal sector grouping configuration.

A. Spanish Airspace structure

The validation scenario was developed in Spanish airspace. In Spain, airspace control is primarily managed through five Air Traffic Services Units (ATSUs), located in Madrid, Barcelona, Seville, Palma de Mallorca, and the Canary Islands.

Barcelona ACC manages the northeastern part of the Iberian Peninsula. Its area of responsibility comprises 17 elementary sectors, which are organised into two sector groupings.

According to current national regulations, the maximum number of sectors permitted for each sector grouping is 10, which therefore sets the limit for Unit Endorsement Validation. In cases where the number of sectors would exceed this limit—as in the case of the Barcelona Route ACC—they must be distributed into different sector groups, what must be done by ASM.

This is a challenging task. For example, in an ATSU containing 15 elementary sectors, these sectors must be combined into sector groupings. When analysing all possible combinations, it becomes evident that number of alternatives runs into thousands, and each of these options would need to be evaluated to ensure the selection of the most optimal solution.

The chosen distribution must ensure compliance with regulatory constraints and allow for optimized staffing and operational flexibility. Once the distribution, i.e. sector groups is decided, it constrains the subsequent processes (such as defining feasible collapsed sectors and sector configurations, figuring out their declared capacity). In other words, it will no longer be possible to use a collapsed sector that combines sectors from different sector groups — even if the traffic load suggests it would be more efficient — because such a collapsed sector would not be supported by the list of sectors within the Unit Endorsement Validation. Consequently, the ATCO would not be authorized to manage it.

Currently in Barcelona Route, the airspace is divided into two clusters (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Barcelona en-route sector groups, West cluster (red) and East cluster (green)

B. Methodology

1) GRU Prototype

In this subsection, the Smart Sector GRoUping (GRU) tool is described, along with its role in supporting the ASM during the strategic phase of defining the groups of sectors that will compose the different clusters (sector groups). The tool is designed to assist in determining the most efficient sector groups by generating a set of indicators for each option, which in turn define the number and scope of Unit Endorsement Licenses assigned to Air Traffic Controllers (ATCOs).

Currently, these decisions rely primarily on the ASM's operational expertise and the historical evolution of sector configurations. The ASM who is familiar with the operational needs of the ATSU, analyses possible combinations and, after a lengthy process of meetings to ensure that both the unit's requirements and the current traffic situation are met, makes the final decision. Typical criteria include rating and rating endorsement requirements, human factors considerations, and geographical or functional sector groupings.

The GRU tool (**Error! Reference source not found.**) aims to formalise and automate this process. It receives as input:

- Historical or forecast traffic data,
- The list of sectors in the ATSU,
- User-defined ATM constraints (more details below).

Using this information the tool generates all possible sector groups combinations based on the principle of geographical adjacency, ensuring that sectors share borders and maintain continuity of traffic flows. For each possibility, it calculates a set of performance indicators to support ASM's decision-making.

The ASM remains responsible for selecting the most suitable option according to their expertise and the operational needs of the ATSU. By comparing the performance indicators across all valid combinations, the ASM can systematically evaluate trade-offs and choose the sector grouping configuration that best aligns with operational objectives and staffing efficiency.

ID	Groups	ATCOs	Sectors
1	Group: CCL, CCU, GO1, GO2, GO3, P2R, VNI Group: GTL, LAG, LVU, MNL, MNU, MSL, MSU, VSL, VSU	2775	54111
4	Group: CCL, CCU, GO2, GO3, GTL, LAG, LVU, P2R, VNI Group: GO1, MNL, MNU, MSL, MSU, VSL, VSU	27518	59203
6	Group: CCL, CCU, GO1, GO3, GTL, LAG, LVU, P2R, VNI Group: GO2, MNL, MNU, MSL, MSU, VSL, VSU	28526	62127
7	Group: CCL, CCU, GO1, GO2, GTL, LAG, LVU, P2R, VNI Group: GO3, MNL, MNU, MSL, MSU, VSL, VSU	27405	59709
11	Group: CCL, CCU, GO1, GO2, GO3, GTL, LAG, LVU, P2R Group: MNL, MNU, MSL, MSU, VNI, VSL, VSU	25768	54388
12	Group: CCL, CCU, GO1, GO2, GO3, GTL, LVU, P2R Group: LAG, LVU, MNL, MNU, MSL, MSU, VNI, VSL, VSU	24463	52638
13	Group: CCL, CCU, GO1, GO2, GO3, LAG, LVU, P2R Group: GTL, LVU, MNL, MNU, MSL, MSU, VNI, VSL, VSU	24436	52403

Figure 8. GRU tool prototype

2) Validation exercise

The purpose of the exercise is to test whether the task of deciding the best sector group configuration for the future of the ATSU becomes simpler and more comprehensive thanks to a tool that provides a set of indicators for each possible sector grouping solution.

As previously explained, the validations were carried out on the Barcelona Route ACC airspace. The process consisted of two runs, both conducted with the collaboration of five expert participants:

- Run 1 – Reference scenario: In this scenario experts must divide Barcelona Route Airspace into two sector groups without support of GRU tool. Experts were supported with historic traffic data information and their own experience. They can share with the other participant their expertise to make the final decision.

- Run 1 – Solution scenario: In this scenario, experts have same objective but, in this case, they can use GRU tool to support their decision.

- Run 2 – Reference scenario: In this scenario, experts must divide the Barcelona Route airspace into three sector groups without the support of the GRU tool. As in Scenario 1 – Reference, the experts are provided with historical traffic data but no computational assistance.

- Run 2 – Solution scenario: In this scenario, experts are tasked with the same objective—dividing the Barcelona Route airspace into three sector groups—but this time with the support of the GRU tool. They can use the tool's indicators and data outputs to assist in the decision-making process.

The process followed for Solution scenarios was:

1. A brief introduction was given about the IFAV project and the expected improvements.
2. The expert receives a brief training session on the tool, including all GRU functionalities, inputs, and outputs.
3. The ASM responsible for creating the sector groups gathers the necessary information for GRU to generate results. This information mainly consists of sector capacities, hourly sector demand for the study period, and valid operational sectors.

4. Once the expert has the information, they configure the necessary user- defined ATM constraints:

- Desired number of sector groups,
- Minimum and maximum number of volumes per group,
- Maximum number of simultaneously active sectors,
- ATCO shift schedules and rest requirements (%),
- IFAV threshold (%): A sector is considered eligible for flexible ATCO rostering application when its traffic demand does not exceed a given percentage of its nominal capacity. This percentage is the IFAV threshold (e.g. 70%).

5. With all these parameters configured, the expert runs the GRU tool and after the execution, they obtain several possible solutions. For any of them, various indicators are offered, allowing selection of the most suitable solution(s). These indicators will be (for each sector group solution):

- Groups: Composition of each sector group in the combination.
- ATCOs: Total number of controllers required over the study period.
- Points: An overload indicator, where lower values reflect fewer overload occurrences.
- Estimated workforce: It is an estimation of the total number of controllers that would be needed with each combination. For this, it is based on the period of highest traffic.
- IFAV Sectors: Total number of hours when at least one sector operates below the IFAV threshold.
- Elasticity: Difference between the maximum and minimum number of open sectors across the study period.
- Sectors: Total number of sector openings across all time intervals.
- Seasonal Indicator: Percentage difference between peak cycle staffing needs and the annual average.
- IFAV Chances: Number of shifts where one group operates an IFAV sector throughout, while another group operates below capacity, indicating potential cross-utilization.
- Non-coincident Peaks: Number of shifts where group demand peaks do not overlap, enabling resource sharing.
- Daily Variation Indicator: A measure of shift uniformity, calculated as:

$$\frac{\sum_1^k(\text{Open sectors})}{\sum_1^k(\text{Max Sectors per Shift} \times \text{Shift Duration})}$$

- CEF4: Annual workforce utilization efficiency, calculated as:

$$100 \times \frac{\sum_1^k(\text{ATCOs})}{\sum_1^k(\text{ATCOs}_{\text{peak}} \times \text{Number of Cycles})}$$

- IFAV Shift (%): Percentage of shifts where at least one group operates below the IFAV threshold.
- Peak Cycle per Group: Peak demand cycle for each sector group.

6. For the validation exercise, the ASM should assess:

- Whether the decision-making process for creating sector groups is simplified thanks to having objective data for each possible solution.
- Whether the time required to reach a decision is reduced compared to the previous approach.
- Whether the information provided by GRU is sufficient to create appropriate sector groups.

The success criterion of the validation exercise was defined as the ASM's ability to determine the most suitable airspace configuration. The exercise was conducted by INECO at its facilities in Madrid, using a laptop as the main equipment.

The validation followed a Human-in-the-Loop approach. In both runs, and after each scenario, experts were asked to complete questionnaires including standardized instruments such as NASA-TLX, SASHA, and SATI, to assess workload, situational awareness, job satisfaction, and related factors.

Additionally, the process incorporated structured documentation consisting of questionnaires and debriefing sessions. These were designed to evaluate different aspects of the GRU tool, such as the clarity and relevance of its indicators, its usability, and the overall improvement in user experience compared to traditional methods.

C. Results

The validation exercise had three main dimensions: 1) operational, 2) human performance, and 3) cost-efficiency.

Related to the operational assessment, it was found that GRU tool proved effective in facilitating the identification of optimal sector groupings. This demonstrates not only its potential applicability under current operational conditions but also its contribution to the IFAV concept by supporting the identification of candidate sectors for flexible endorsement. The validation further confirmed that the indicators generated by the tool were sufficient and relevant to enable ASMs to make informed decisions. A detailed analysis showed that GRU provides essential insights that are not available through traditional methods.

In terms of human performance, it was studied whether the proposed method was comprehensive, supported human decision-making, and could be applied effectively under normal operational conditions. The allocation of tasks between human actors and the system was judged to be appropriate, while the technical system and interface were evaluated as effective in supporting the task. Participants expressed positive acceptance of the solution, with competence requirements and training needs clearly identified and considered manageable.

Regarding cost-efficiency, the analysis indicated that annual workforce requirements could be reduced while overall productivity increased.

Once explained the three dimensions separately, following are some quantitative figures that complement and provide a more detailed view of the tool's performance:

- Overall workload decreased by approximately 40%, with participants reporting a substantial reduction in both perceived cognitive and operational demands when using GRU for decision-making.
- Trust in the tool increased by around 30%, as users expressed greater confidence in GRU's outputs compared to traditional planning methods.
- Decision-making support improved by 50%, with the tool perceived as a valuable enabler for more robust and data-driven strategic planning.
- Preference for GRU was twice as high as for legacy methods, indicating a strong inclination among participants to adopt GRU for future planning exercises.
- Job satisfaction increased by approximately 40%, with GRU perceived as streamlining complex tasks and enhancing both efficiency and workplace satisfaction.
- Potential improvements in ATCO productivity were estimated at 1-5% according to CEF2 metrics, aligning with the objective of improving cost efficiency.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

We demonstrated the benefits of the SSG strategy for enhancing the flexibility of ATCO deployment through two complementary use-case scenarios. The results confirmed both the efficiency and operational feasibility of the strategy, while providing key indicators to support decision-making in sector grouping and ATCO rostering processes. From a human performance perspective, the solution was well received by experts. Specifically, task allocation, technical support, and training requirements were considered appropriate and manageable. Notably, the SSG strategy's effectiveness is rooted in its consideration of critical parameters, particularly geography and traffic flows. Furthermore, the cost-efficiency analysis showed potential to reduce annual workforce requirements while simultaneously enhancing overall productivity, reinforcing the tool's value as a practical and sustainable solution for future operations.

While the concept has already been successfully validated, future enhancements would focus on incorporating additional operational dimensions—such as hand-over timing during sector transitions, inter-controller coordination, and procedural diversity across ATSUs. By integrating operational, scientific, and technical knowledge, these steps represent valuable opportunities to further strengthen the scalability of the SSG framework and ensure even greater alignment with real-world practices. Additionally, to maximise the benefits of SSG, it is recommended to apply it across neighbouring ATSUs or ANSPs.

Looking ahead, a dissemination campaign is recommended to showcase the tools' usability and benefits, supported by trials in diverse operational environments to broaden validation. Presentations to the SESAR Deployment Manager could

position SSG as a candidate solution within the Common Project pipeline. Further scalability assessments in complex settings will help confirm its applicability and support its integration into the European ATM network.

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